

A STUDY ON CONTACT STRESS AND WEAR ANALYSIS FOR BALL BEARING MATERIAL USING COMPUTER AIDED SIMULATION

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Abstract

Rolling element bearings are mostly used in rotating machineries and consider as a most critical component. Ball bearings are generally used, such as electric motors, material handling systems, turbines, generators, fan, pumps and compressors, etc. is essential equipment in engineering plants. Wear failure constantly occurs before fatigue failure during the operation of bearings in good conditions. Therefore, wear life is a critical property of a deep groove ball bearing. Wear life is a critical property of ball bearings. The limited existing methods for wear life are attributed to the complexity of wear effects of rolling bearings. Ball bearings are often exposed to high stress level at the contact and extreme application environment combining wear, high temperature, etc. Therefore, wear resistance of the balls under high loads is critical for extending the lifetime of the ball bearing and cutting the cost and time on repairing and replacement. The objective this work is to define the wear properties of ball bearing material for composites of Aluminum Composites. Polymer Composites and Ceramic Composites. Different materials are selected under the above-mentioned categories. Tribological Behavior of the materials is studied for different materials. The materials will be tested under the Pin on disc measurement to determine the Co-efficient of friction and wear rate. Comparative Study of all the composite material will be done with the stainless steel which is currently used in the rotor bearing.

Keywords: Ball Bearing, Rolling Element Bearings, Computer Aided Simulation, Finite Element Analysis (FEA), CAD Modelling, ANSYS Simulation, Thermal Effects on Bearings, Microstructural Analysis, etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bearing in Electric Rotor

Figure 1 Bearing in Electric Rotor

Bearings are highly engineered, precision-made components that enable machinery to move at extremely high speeds and carry remarkable loads with ease and efficiency. A bearing is a machine element that constrains relative motion to only the desired motion, and reduces friction between moving parts.[4]

Bearings are components designed to connect machine parts and they transmit motion and forces. They are usually mounted on axles or shafts and inserted in housings. They sustain severe static as well as cyclic loads while serving reliably in difficult environments in both the radial and axial directions. [4] There are several bases for classification of bearings; we will discuss all of them one by one.

Depending on the direction of force

- a) Radial bearing

- b) Axial bearing
- c) Depending on the type of friction
- d) Sliding contact bearing
- e) Roller contact bearing [2.8]

Component of Ball Bearing

Figure 2 Components of Ball Bearing

The ball Bearing consists of Outer ring and Inner ring which are in contact with source and application. The bearing rotates about its own axis with help of balls which are constrained in the cage of the bearing. The current study focuses on balls of bearing. [13]

Failures Occurring in Ball Bearing

Figure 3 Failures Occurring in Bearing Materials

As a main criterion for the functionality of the particular bearing type the Frictional Model which considers the comparison between sliding friction MSL and rolling friction MRR is used.[3]

The standard takes into account factors like misalignment, clearance, internal load distribution, lubrication and cleanliness. This proves that lubrication and wear failure has a vital role for the bearing performance and might increase the service life of a motor [3]

Literature Summary

Table 1 Literature summary

Research Summary	References
Wear Analysis for bearing made of GCr15 Using Archard Theory of contact stress wear analysis	[3]
Comparison of Brass and Bronze balls on Steel using Wear test for Sliding Velocity 1m/s to 3m/s	[7]
Fretting wear on bearing material and wear due to over rolling of balls	[9]
Basic causes of bearing failure and Dynamic requirement of bearing material for vibrational response	[10]
Fault Tree analysis for Electrical Rotor bearing. Considering Abrasive, Adhesive, Erosive and Wear Fatigue, Fretting wear	[11]
Bearing Failure due to formation of cracks, indentations and wear out surfaces	[9]
Tribological behavior and properties of PTFE (Graphite), Nickel, Nickel Chrome, Molybdenum Disulphide and Nylon.	[13]
Mathematical modelling and calculations for Load acting on ball race, Pressure, Frictional resistance and frictional torque.	[15]

Research Gap: Bearing life mainly depends upon the choice of bearing material, so it is important to select the bearing material correctly to service conditions and operating mode. The coefficient of friction of stainless steel 0.08-0.14. The current material used in the bearing is Ceramic Composite. Hence an attempt is made to study the wear rate investigation of Ceramic material as well as stainless steel as a replacement. The main objective for the bearing is to provide Low coefficient of friction, good wear

behavior, High compressive strength, and Structural uniformity and Corrosion resistance.

PROBLEM DEFINATION

“To analyze the Tribological wear behavior of different Ceramic and Polymer Composite Material for balls in bearing of electric rotor”

Generally, the wear analysis of certain materials is done on Pin o Disc setup which is conceptually called as Tribometer setup. In this paper, numerical methodology has been developed using Finite Element Methodology method for determination of contact stress and wear deformation under the operating conditions. In this concept, an attempt is made to replace the ball bearing materials like Steel which are widely used in industry by Ceramic and Polymer materials. These materials are investigated in order to find the possible consequences of wear and Contact Stresses.

The objectives of this research are:

- Analyze the properties of Ceramics and Polymer Composites materials for Wear requirement.
- To select best possible material for balls of ball bearing used in Electric rotor.
- To develop the numerical methodology in computer aided software for determination of wear and contact stresses.
- To test the wear behavior of different composites and steel for wear rate and volume.
- To determine the contact stress behavior by using contact Stress analysis theory.

Wear Requirement Of Bearing

Figure 4 Different Types of wear

Tribology is defined as the science and technology of interacting surfaces in relative motion, having its origin in the Greek word ‘tribos’ meaning rubbing. [14].

Wear is progressive loss or removal of material from one or both the surfaces in contact as the result of relative motion between them. [11] Wear is the single most influencing factor which shortens the effective life of machine or its components. [14]

It is a process of removal of material from solid surfaces either one or both of two in solid state contact, when two solid surfaces are in sliding or rolling motion together. [13]

Component Selection

Figure 5 Bearing 6302

The 6302 is a 15 mm Ball Bearing that can be used in many rotary and factory automation applications. The 6302 Deep Groove Ball Bearings is an open style bearing. The 6302Z ball bearing is a single row raceway and single shielded. The 6302ZZ ball bearing has a single row raceway and it is shielded on each side. [2.8]

TABLE-1 DIMENSIONAL PROPERTIES OF BEARINGS 6302

Parameter	Notation	Value
Bore Diameter	d	15 mm
Housing Diameter	D	42 mm
Width of Bearing	B	13 mm
Diameter if Inner Race	d1	23.7 mm
Diameter if Outer Race	D2	36.23 mm
Fillet Radius.	r1,2	min. 1 mm

TABLE 2 FUNCTIONAL OF BEARINGS 6302

Parameter	Value
Basic dynamic load rating C	11.9 KN
Basic static load rating C0	5.4 KN
Fatigue load limit Pu	0.228 KN
Reference speed	38000 r/min
Limiting speed	24000 r/min
Mass	0.082 Kg
Calculation Factor F0	12

Finite Element Analysis for Contact Stress Analysis

a). Computer Model and FEA:

Figure 6 Computer Model of Bearing 6302 Prepared in Creo Software

The dimensions of the bearing are stated in the table 1, with the help of which the model is created in creo 3.0 software.

Figure 7 Modeling of Component

The Bearing model is first modeled in the Creo software of Version 3.0. The Creo file is further saved in IGES to call in Ansys.

Figure 8 Contact Setting for Balls and Inner/Outer Race

The contact setting describes and initialized the nature of contact between the two bodies. The Ansys provides four types of contacts which are, Frictional, Frictionless, Rough and No Support. Hence in this case frictional contact is been subjected between the Inner Race (Contact) and Balls.

Figure 9 Inertion of Revolute Joint

Revolute Joint in Ansys is the application of the rotating components. As shown in the figure 8 the inner race is subjected to as rotational movement of which the bearing capacity is described.

Figure 10 Subjecting the load and Rotational Displacement

The bearing is designed for loading capacity of 10KN. Hence the load is subjected to required condition and analysis is done.

Results for Finite Element Analysis for Contact Stress

Figure 11 Contact Stress Analysis of Balls made of Stainless Steel

Figure 12 Contact Stress Analysis of Balls made of Silicon Nitride

Figure 13 Contact Stress Analysis of Balls made of Zirconium Oxide

Figure 14 Contact Stress Analysis of Balls made of Aluminium oxide

2. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS FOR WEAR DEFORMATION

Ansys Setting for Transient Structural Analysis

The Wear Deformation Analysis in Working Environment Can Be Done in Transient Structural Module of Ansys Workbench. This Module Performs the Analysis by Providing the Working Environment Conditions and Results Can Be Determined for All the Stress-Strain Properties.

Figure 15 Applying the Constraints

the bearing when attached with the shaft, is press fit inside the hole. hence due to which the upper race of bearing is kept fixed as shown in the fig. 15.

Figure 16 Application of Speed to Inner Race

The capacity of bearing under loading conditions is considered as 1000rpm. Hence the rotational velocity of the inner race is applied as shown in the figure 15 of 105 rad/sec.

Figure 17 Application of Speed to Inner Race

It is assumed as; the speed of rolling of balls is 1:10 as that of the bearing inner race. Hence the implementation of velocity for balls is provided as 10.5 rad/sec as shown in figure 17.

FEA Results for Wear Deformation Analysis.

Figure 18 Results of Wear Analysis for Balls made of Stainless Steel

Figure 19 Results of Wear Analysis for Balls made of Silicon Nitride

Figure 20 Results of Wear Analysis for Balls made of Zirconium Oxide

Figure 217 Results of Wear Analysis for Balls made of Aluminum Oxide

The results in Figure 17, 18, 19 and 20 respectively, shows the wear deformation produced when the bearing is running at the speed of 1000 rpm and frictional contact for Coefficient of friction of 0.2 which is considered as maximum and equivalent for all the materials.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Contact Stress Analysis

The table 4 shows the results for FEA obtained in the contact stress analysis subjected to the bearing under stationary condition. The results described below are for equivalent stress and deformation produced.

TABLE 4 RESULTS OF CONTACT STRESS ANALYSIS

Material	Equivalent Stress (MPa)	Deformation (mm)
Stainless Steel	84.77	0.032
Silicon Nitride	80.95	0.030
Zirconium dioxide	91.05	0.036
Aluminum Oxide	82.31	0.031

Figure 22 Comparison of Equivalent Stress for Contact Stress Analysis

Figure 23 Comparison of Deformation for Contact Stress Analysis

- The Figure 23, show the comparison of results that are determined for contact stress analysis.
- As we can see from the above figure 23, for all the static loading conditions, the stress produced for all the materials is similar. Still, with the keen and accurate comparison, the stress obtained in the Silicon Nitride and Aluminum Oxide is the lowest as per the Stainless Steel.
- As we can see from the above figure 23, for all the static loading conditions, the deformation produced for, the stress obtained in the Silicon Nitride and Aluminum Oxide is the lowest as per the Stainless Steel.
- In both the results for contact stress, the deformation of Zirconium Oxide is obtained to be maximum.

Transient Structural Analysis for Wear Deformation:

Table 5 results Of Wear Deformation Analysis

Material	Deformation (mm)
Stainless Steel	12.17
Silicon Nitride	10.43
Zirconium dioxide	12.75
Aluminum Oxide	13.91

Figure 24 Comparison of Results for Wear Deformation

The Figure-24, show the comparison of results that are determined for transient Structural analysis for wear rate deformation. As we can see from the above figure-24, for all the dynamic loading conditions, the deformation produced for, the stress results obtained in the Silicon Nitride and aluminum Oxide is the lowest as per the Stainless Steel. The Wear obtained in the Aluminum Oxide is maximum amongst all.

4. CONCLUSIONS

- In this paper, the numerical analysis and material optimization of balls made Stainless Steel is done with the replacement of Ceramic Matrix Composites.
- All the loading constraints have been studied and applied to determine the loading conditions that can be used for FEA.
- FEA is done in Ansys software for determination of wear deformation for Transient Structural Analysis. The wear rate of Silicon Nitride is found to be minimum whereas the other materials are also similar to the stainless steel.
- If the contact stress analysis criteria is considered, the equivalent stress formed in stainless steel is found to be 84 MPa, where as that of Zirconium is 91 MPa. If the stress criteria is considered, the magnitude of stress found in Silicon Nitride and Aluminum Oxide is 80 and 82 MPa which are somewhat similar to the Stainless-steel bearing.
- The wear deformation is determined using the transient structural analysis which states the least wear in Silicon Nitride with 10mm whereas the wear for steel is 12mm, for zirconium is 12.75mm and for Alumina is 13mm which are somewhat similar.
- The Numerical method is less time consuming, and hence can be used as initial purposed testing methodology for design of balls under different material optimization.
- Numerical Method is also cost saving technique, as there is no need of manufacturing specimens or the testing setup

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